

Consciousness system approaches and the financial instruments

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Abstract:

Understanding the business planning of companies and their financial instruments is impossible without understanding consciousness as a cross-section network. The present study introduces a specific approach to the structure of consciousness, in the mirror of professional literature approaches. The world of business and basic economic models are comprised of complex elements. The appearance of human decisions in accounting reports is one of the end points of this consciousness. International Business Planning and its partial elements, Financial Instruments are the end points of Conscious Business and the entire superstructure. The complete structure is arranged according to the same basic principles. Financial processes can be parallel modelled from multiple aspects with quantum processes. Fundamentally, the appearance of human decisions in accounting reports is one of the end points of limitless consciousness. The conscious organization as a constantly learning innovative organization. The factors of consciousness are valid for the conscious business as well. The test of a truly conscious company is the capacity to learn from experiences, and thereby its capability to grow, to become even stronger and more committed in the direction of consciousness. Consciousness, just as company business planning has a survival value. Just as in the case of an individual, business planning, as one of the manifestations of consciousness, provides operational advantages to the organization. Consciousness as a concept has become a defining factor of business planning. The model and the selection system are applicable to all areas of economics, and can be further developed independent of the type of company groups.

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1. Introduction

The world of business and basic economic models are comprised of complex elements. Besides conventional sociological approaches the elements are part of the integration of natural science principles, such as neuroscience and brain research. We can consider the most fundamental question regarding consciousness that consciousness is what is capable of creating the stationary waves constituting matter, the entire electromagnetic spectrum that is known as the material world, and of course the physical body and the brain as well. Thus, such abstract concept systems attributed to be a creation of human thinking as the world of the international corporate system, business and financial systems, are also parts of this consciousness. Their functioning is characterized by conscious arrangement (Behe, 1996). There is an accepted theory in international neuroscience, according to which the human brain is incapable of creating a non-material entity - let's call it mind, self-awareness, free will, a soul, but mostly the combination of these - that acts as a controller of the network of neurons which created it (Szőnyi, 2011; Freud, 2005). Sisodia and Kaufman place consciousness in the central element of human life (Sisodia, 2009; Kaufman, 2006). In connection to their knowledge and actions humans are generally directly conscious of their goals. They know what they intend to do. The conscious processes (consciousness) of humans are constantly changing processes, which are influenced by their observations, thoughts and emotions that arise at a specific moment. Conscious processes have two basic functions: (i) monitoring (constant monitoring of the external environment of humans and their internal patterns), and (ii) the panning of goals (in the case of actions directed at the environment as well as in the case of the necessary transformation of internal patterns) (Pléh, 1998; Bóta 2014).

The conscious and disregard others. The selected information most frequently signals the changes occurring in the environment or the internal world (Pléh, 1998; Bóta, 2014). The other function of the conscious processes of humans is the planning and re-planning of goals, as well as the guidance of processes of humans monitor the events ongoing in their environment as well as in their internal world by observation. As a result of the extreme amount of information a kind of selectivity can be seen in the conscious processes of humans, they highlight certain signals of the unconscious processes our actions. During the planning, in our consciousness we must project events that have not taken place yet with such that will occur in the future, meaning that we must imagine the possible scenarios and choose from among them, as well as take the steps necessary for their realization. In this complex task sequence there are a great many unconscious processes, but the formulation of goals is performed by conscious human processes. (Pléh, 1998; Bóta, 2014)

2. Finding and discussion: The structure of consciousness

I conducted the professional literature review regarding the structure of consciousness and its characteristics while taking into consideration the structure of the work of Whitney, which I detailed below (Whitney, 2015). I conducted the professional literature review similarly to the superstructure of consciousness. Consciousness or Unified Field, which is the foundation of every studied structure. The appearance of human decisions in accounting reports is one of the end points of this consciousness. The Economics of Consciousness and Quantum Economics are one of the largest sets, which encompass and permeate Conscious Capitalism. The appearing partial sets of these are Conscious Companies, Conscious Leadership and Conscious Business. International Business Planning and its partial elements, Financial Instruments (balance sheet items, the items and indicators of profit reports) are the end

points of Conscious Business and the entire superstructure. The complete structure is arranged according to the same basic principles.

2.1. Consciousness or Unified Field

Clear Mind, Consciousness and the Unified Field are at the foundation of every intellect and everything material that exists. All materials, all tangible existing entities arise from this field. It constitutes the substantive core of life – a gigantic unified field, which expresses and permeates the entire visible world of all phenomena. (Hagelin, 1987) The conscious characteristic of this unified field is clear mind, which is such an abstract limitless consciousness field that cannot be described in the light of objective or personal experiences in any way (Hagelin, 1987). Currently one of the best models describing consciousness is the *Integrated Information Theory* developed by Tononi. According to Tononi's theory, for us to be able to state that a system is conscious, it must integrate data in a way that the system as a whole will comprise more information than the sum of its parts.

Consciousness appears in those systems that contain numerous different and interconnected information units. Starting from this premise, consciousness becomes measurable, as a theoretical quantity. (Tononi, 2008)

Equation 1: Definition of consciousness (Tononi, 2008):

$$\Phi(X(\text{mech}, x_1)) = H[p(X_0(\text{mech}, x_1)) | \prod p({}^k M_0(\text{mech}, \mu_1))] \text{ for } {}^k M_0 \in \text{MIP}$$

Where:

$p(X_0(\text{mech}, x_1))$ = the probability distribution of the entire system

$\prod p({}^k M_0(\text{mech}, \mu_1))$ = the probability distribution of a portion of the entire system

x = system elements

${}^k M_{\text{system}}$ = sub-elements

Φ = integrated information

I = Information

O = Integration

MIP = minimum information partition

Equation 2: Condition proving the existence of consciousness (Tononi, 2008):

$$\Phi(X(\text{mech}, x_1)) > 0$$

where:

Φ = integrated information

$(X_0(\text{mech}, x_1))$ = the entire system

2.2. Economics of Consciousness and Quantum Economics

I identify Quantum Economics as the economics of business, in other words Economics of Consciousness. (Goswami, 2016). Among the basic elements of Quantum Economics the production of profit is not the exclusive and ultimate goal. The basic elements of Quantum Economics are recognizable in the following elements: (i) the production and sales of companies show a positive and growing trend (ii) the value creation of companies increases employee retention (iii) they prevent employee fluctuation in the company (iv) the companies create jobs in the sectors where the companies directly or indirectly operate (v) the companies are creative and innovative, thereby they also contribute to employee retention (vi) the companies have a positive effect on the local community. (Goswami, 2016)

Quantum Economics applies the methods of quantum physics in the areas of economics and business sciences. Financial processes can be parallel modelled from multiple aspects with quantum processes. (Shubik, 1999; Haven, 2002; Baaquie, 2007; Haven and Khrennikov 2013; Orrell, 2016; Orell and Chlupaty 2016; Colin, 2017). According to Asghar Qadir, an early proponent of Quantum Economics, the particles described in quantum mechanics "the individual as an entity can be considered a dot in the Hilbert-space." (Qadir, 1978)

Equation 3: Appearance of the individual as a decision maker in quantum space. (Qadir,1978):

$$L: (P) \rightarrow (q)$$

where: P and q are dots (persons) that exist in the S space

L: linear operator

Aerts carried on Asghar's train of thought, and with the epsilon-model concluded that multiple aspects of human decision making, including those participating in economic decisions, follow a kind of quantum logic. (Aerts and Aerts, 1994) Fundamentally, the appearance of human decisions in accounting reports is one of the end points of this limitless consciousness (Helfert, 2001; Virág et al, 2013).

2.3. Conscious Capitalism

According to Sisodia, companies operating in the model of Conscious Capitalism show that enterprises are the true value creators. They apply creative business models that are transformative as well as inspirational, and they assist in solving many of the world's social and environmental problems. One of the most important characteristics of companies that apply Conscious Capitalism is that they are guided by goals which are higher than just maximizing profit. A well thought through goal energizes the enterprise and supplies it with passion and creativity. Conscious Capitalism is a business paradigm that creates diverse values and well-being for all stakeholders: including financial, intellectual, physical, ecological, social, cultural, emotional, ethical and even spiritual areas. This is a business approach that is more aware of higher goals and their influence exerted on the world. Deeper consciousness is reflected by the reason for our existence, to find ways to create value. (Mackey and Sisodia, 2014). According to Chong Wang, the theory of Conscious Capitalism is a generally applicable but inconsistent theory. Consciousness by itself does not guarantee that the companies will perform excellently from a financial aspect. (Wang, 2013)

2.4. Conscious Companies

The literature discussing the consciousness of organizations was processed in detail by Marja Turunen. I describe the cornerstones of conscious companies included in professional literature partially based on this. Heaton and Harung see the conscious organization as a constantly learning innovative organization. (Heaton and Harung, 1999). The concept of company consciousness was seen in the 1990s by Campion and Palmer as a completely new paradigm that is related to awareness and information processing. Specifically, they define company consciousness as a group of consciously formulated and shared values that motivate and guide individuals to act as the interests of the business organization require it. Campion and Palmer questioned the usefulness of studying company consciousness. They do not dispute the value and usefulness of the design, but they dispute the *refraction* of the

definition. (Campion and Palmer, 1996). In contrast with this, Lavine and Moore maintain that the consciousness of an organization is connected to the individual, as the collective consciousness of abstractions created by humans. (Lavine and Moore 1996). Pruzan considers an organization as a societal system that has the capacity of self-reproduction and characterizes itself (Pruzan, 2001). Pandey and Gupta connect the features of human consciousness with the potential behavior of business organizations. (Pandey and Gupta 2008).

From the organizational aspect Gustavson and Harung use the expression of collective consciousness. Pruzan, Gustavson and Harung, and Heaton and Harung suggest that the collective consciousness of an organization appears in its most important motivators, in its behavior and development. (Pruzan, 2001; Gustavson and Harung 1994; Heaton and Harung 1999) Collective consciousness is an experience based *transcendent structure* that is shared by groups of humans. Various capabilities and intelligence is connected to different levels of consciousness. The different levels of consciousness can be described with the various levels of organizational identity. (Hermel et al, 2003; Wilber 2000; Collins and Chippendale 1995; Wilber, 2000; Rasberry, 2000). Consciousness is created when matter, meaning the nervous system, reaches a certain level of complexity. (Delbrück, 1986) Consciousness is independent of matter, and matter is not the foundation of self-consciousness. Materialist as well as dualist approaches have been able to define consciousness. (Von-Roos, 1995) A conscious organization is capable of liberating the human power of *introspection and reflexivity*, and shows the capacities necessary for renewal, adaptation and transformation. The level of collective consciousness is visible in organizational creativity and innovation. (Milliman, 2001; Quatro, 2004) The creation of complex company strategies operating in a complex environment exceeds the limited rational decision making ability. (Bakonyi, 2014) The company strategy is the end result of a conscious analysis process, in which the decision makers are limitedly rational. (Bakonyi, 2014) Roels compared the company to the patterns of living biological organisms, and he demonstrated similarities with them from multiple aspects. In relation to the nature and development of companies he concluded that companies are *dissipative structures*. (Roels, 2012)

2.5. Conscious Leadership

In a conscious company organization leadership and management are highly decentralized and include a much higher level of autonomy and team based work. The leadership task of a conscious business is to establish the conditions that allow employees to be self-governed and self-organized. In a conscious business the participating persons are self-motivated. (Sisodia, 2012) Self-conscious companies are more capable in managing their multinational capital investments than companies that are not self-conscious. (Iouliano et al, 2017)

2.6. Conscious Business

A Conscious Business means the mutual dependence of stakeholders. The six most important stakeholders (clients, employees, investors, suppliers, society and environment) are mutually dependent on each other, and their goal is the creation of a win-win-win-win-win-win business strategy. (Mackey, 2011)

The factors of consciousness are valid for the conscious business as well. According to Sisodia, the test of a truly conscious company is the capacity to learn from experiences, and thereby

its capability to grow, to become even stronger and more committed in the direction of consciousness. (Sarkar, 2017)

2.7. International Business Planning and Financial Instruments

Professional literature differentiates between the so-called business plan and the so-called international business plan. According to the basic conclusion of the authors, Brinckmann et al. (2010), business planning is a culture dependent phenomenon. Business processes must be planned. In these business processes one of the features of consciousness is the existence of planning. Planning is one of the functions of consciousness.

According to the co-authors, Brown and Gutterman (2003), national and international business planning possesses similar structures, and they are identical in a multitude of points. According to the author, Willer, business success and financial planning are closely related, they are directly proportional to each other (Willer, 2007), and this may even project a higher level of consciousness. According to some earlier interpretations in professional literature, such as Ackoff and Emery, the source of a company's consciousness was seen in the business management of the company, which used the organization as an instrument for the achievement of its goals. In contrast with this, the higher the level of autonomy delegated to company sub-systems, the less we can speak of a (uniform) company consciousness even metaphorically. (Ackoff and Emery, 1972) This opinion is represented by Andrews who displayed one of the paradigms of the 1980s, according to which there is no such management system that can take the place of the individual who forms a clear image of right and wrong. (Andrews, 1980). In contrast with all of this, according to Singer similarly to consciousness, business planning also represents survival values and operational advantages. Since the middle of the 1950s strategic planning can be considered crucial and as a key success factor to companies. (Turkay et al, 2012). According to Sperry, the increasingly complex and complicated company operations and structure that formed in the 1960s mirror the organic patterns of the functioning of the human body. Consciousness, just as company business planning has a survival value. Just as in the case of an individual, business planning, as one of the manifestations of consciousness, provides operational advantages to the organization. The organic system of the human brain is similar to the decision making control system which is monitored by value priorities, and in which conscious phenomena provide certain operational advantages that can be adapted to consciousness-independent systems as well. (Sperry,1979)

3. Conclusion

Consciousness as a concept has become a defining factor of business planning. Its own place in concept systems developed gradually. The fundamental factors of consciousness are clearly visible in professional literature as well, such as in the case of Sperry.

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